

Data Management Plan Template

The aim of this template¹ and guidance (text in italics/grey) is to assist in preparing Data Management Plans (DMP) for FLUP’s Master Dissertations and Doctoral Theses, as well as for Grant Applications and Research Projects.

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PROJECT – GENERAL INFORMATION	
TYPE:	
ID:	
ACRONYM:	
NAME:	
PI:	
INSTITUTION(S):	
PERIOD:	
WEBSITE:	

PROJECT - ABSTRACT	
KEYWORDS:	

¹ This document is primarily based on the Horizon Europe guidelines and adapted from the FCT Data Management Plan template.

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN – HISTORY OF CHANGES

VERSION	PUBLICATION DATE	CONTRIBUTOR(S)	CHANGE(S)

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN – ANNEXES

DOCUMENT	SHORT DESCRIPTION/URI
<i>DEspacho GR 12_10_2024_Politica de Ciência Aberta-merged.pdf</i>	<i>U.Porto policy on Open Science. https://sigarra.up.pt/up/pt/LEGISLACAO_GERAL.ver_legislacao?p_nr=48092</i>

1. DATA INFORMATION

1.1	Will you reuse existing data for this project? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
1.1.1	If Yes, which existing data will be reused and under which terms of use?
1.1.2	If Yes, which data type(s) and format(s) will be reused?
1.2	Will new data be created and/or produced in this project? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
1.2.1	If Yes, which data will be created and/or produced and under which terms of use?
1.2.2	If Yes, which data type(s) and format(s) will be created and/or produced?
1.3	How much data storage will this project require in total? <input type="checkbox"/> 0 – 10 GB <input type="checkbox"/> 100 – 1000 GB <input type="checkbox"/> 10 – 100 GB <input type="checkbox"/> >1000 GB
1.4	To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside this project?

2. DOCUMENTATION AND METADATA	
2.1	What documentation will accompany the data?
2.2	Will there be metadata associated with the data? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes Language: _____ <input type="checkbox"/> No
2.2.1	If Yes, will the metadata follow any standard(s)?
2.2.2	Will the data use controlled vocabularies? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

3. STORAGE AND SECURITY OF DATA AND METADATA	
3.1	Is there a policy in place for data storage and backups during the project? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
3.2	Where will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?
3.3	How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research? <input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable (no sensitive data). <input type="checkbox"/> Default security measures of the institution networked research storage. <input type="checkbox"/> Additional security measures.

4. PERSONAL DATA, INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS, AND OWNERSHIP	
4.1	Will you process and/or store personal data during the project? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
4.1.1	If Yes, how will compliance with legislation and (institutional) regulation on personal data be ensured?
4.2	How will ownership of the data and intellectual property rights to the data be managed?

5. DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION	
5.1	How will data be selected for long-term preservation? <input type="checkbox"/> All data resulting from the project will be preserved for at least __ years. <input type="checkbox"/> Other.

5.2	<p>What data will be made available for reuse?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> All data resulting from the project will be made available. <input type="checkbox"/> Other.</p>
5.3	<p>When will the data be available for reuse and for how long will the data be available?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Data available as soon as archived in repository.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Data available as soon as article is published.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Data available upon completion of the project.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Data available after completion of project (with embargo).</p>
5.4	<p>In which repository/archive will the data be deposited and made available for reuse?</p>
5.5	<p>Does the repository support persistent identifiers (PID)?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes PID: _____ <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unknown</p>
5.6	<p>Under which license will the data be archived and made available for reuse?</p>
5.7	<p>Will there be a strategy for publishing specific tools or software generated in this project?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
5.8	<p>Will there be other research outputs?</p>

6. RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES	
6.1	<p>Who will be responsible for data management?</p>
6.2	<p>What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)?</p>